

ARIES

Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 730871

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Irradiation test results

DELIVERABLE: D17.3

Document identifier:	ARIES_De17-3
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 54 (October 2021)
Report release date:	17/11/2021
Work package:	WP17: Materials for extreme thermal management (PowerMat)
Lead beneficiary:	POLITO
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

In this report, we present the main results of several irradiation campaigns performed from 2019 to 2021 at the UNILAC M-Branch facility of GSI and HiRadMat facility at CERN on various graphitic and diamond-based materials. Two types of irradiation effects were analysed: long-term dose accumulation effects using 4.8 MeV/u Ca ions irradiation at the UNILAC accelerator at GSI and transient effects induced by the impact of high intensity, short pulse particle beam on targets both at the HiRadMat facility at CERN, using 440 GeV proton beams, and at UNILAC using 1.1 GeV U ions.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730871. ARIES began in May 2017 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	C. Accettura	CERN	01/10/21
	F. Carra	CERN	
	Philipp Bolz	GSI	
Edited by	A. Morena	POLITO	12/10/21
Reviewed by	L. Peroni [Task coordinator]	POLITO	28/10/21
	M. Tomut [WP coordinator]	GSI,	
	A. Bertarelli [WP coordinator]	WWU Munster CERN	
Approved by	Steering Committee		17/11/21

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	5
2. LONG-TERM IRRADIATION EFFECTS IN MATERIALS FOR HL-LHC COLLIMATORS	6
2.1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATIONS	6
2.2 GRAPHITE-BASED MATERIALS.....	7
2.2.1 <i>Evolution of electrical resistivity</i>	7
2.2.2 <i>Raman spectroscopy</i>	9
2.2.3 <i>Thermal annealing</i>	13
2.3 METALLIC COATINGS	15
2.3.1 <i>Evolution of electrical resistivity</i>	15
2.3.2 <i>Microscopic investigation</i>	16
3. SHORT TERM IRRADIATION: THERMOMECHANICAL DYNAMIC EFFECTS	19
3.1 MULTIMAT-1	19
3.1.1 <i>Test bench</i>	19
3.1.2 <i>Material samples</i>	21
3.1.3 <i>Experiment parameters</i>	22
3.1.4 <i>Results</i>	23
3.2 MULTIMAT-2	33
3.2.1 <i>Goals</i>	33
3.2.2 <i>Experimental setup</i>	34
3.2.3 <i>Preliminary results and planned PIE</i>	36
3.3 DYNAMIC RESPONSE OF ISOTROPIC GRAPHITE IMPACTED BY U BEAM AT UNILAC, GSI – EFFECT OF RADIATION DAMAGE ACCUMULATION	38
4. CONCLUSIONS	42
REFERENCES	43

Executive summary

In this report, we present the main results of several irradiation campaigns performed from 2017 to 2021 at the UNILAC M-Branch facility of GSI and HiRadMat facility at CERN on various graphitic and diamond-based materials. Two types of irradiation effects were analysed in this experimental campaign: long-term dose accumulation effects using 4.8 MeV/u Ca ions irradiation at the M-Branch beamline of the UNILAC accelerator at GSI and transient effects such as pressure waves, induced by the impact of high intensity, short pulse particle beam on targets both at the HiRadMat facility at CERN, using 440 GeV proton beams and at M3, UNILAC, at GSI, using 1.1 GeV U ions.

In the experiments carried out with Ca ions at UNILAC in 2019, materials samples were irradiated at different ion fluences to study the degradation of properties as a function of the displacement per atom (dpa). Particular attention was paid to the changes at increasing values of dpa of the electrical resistivity and of the microscopic structure. The observed degradation of electrical properties was analysed and compared to the expected radiation level of HL-LHC.

The methods and the theories developed in this work can be applied in future irradiation campaigns to extend the statistic and the understanding of relevant phenomena. In particular, a new Ca-ion irradiation campaign was carried out at GSI in March 2021 focusing on the study the effects of the dpa rate on the microscopic and electrical changes of materials.

In other experiments performed at the M3 beamline at UNILAC accelerator at GSI, a high intensity Uranium ion beam with a pulse duration of 100 μ s impacted a thin graphite target. For the first time in such experiments, the evolution of beam-induced stress waves with accumulated radiation damage was monitored and the change in elastic modulus of the irradiated material was calculated.

In October 2017 an experiment making use of a modular, reusable test bench (Multimat) was performed at CERN HiRadMat facility with the goal of gathering experimental data upon which building or validating reliable constitutive models for a wide variety of materials meant to be used in beam-interacting devices, particularly collimators, subjected to potentially destructive events caused by the impact of energetic particle beams.

The behaviour of the tested samples was monitored online relying on embarked sensors and remote instrumentation. Intensities, profiles and frequencies of the stress waves measured on the outer surfaces of the samples were benchmarked against those predicted by numerical simulations, allowing to derive the safety factor for materials to be used in HL-LHC collimators.

In September 2021, a new experiment (Multimat-2) was performed at HiRadMat, exploiting the same test-bench and using the same techniques, to test and validate those materials and thin-films which were successively developed and produced.

1. Introduction

This document reports the main results of irradiation tests performed in WP17.3. Two types of irradiation effects were analysed in this experimental campaign: long-term irradiation effect at the M-Branch beamline of the UNILAC accelerator at GSI and short pulse particle beam effects both at the HiRadMat facility at CERN, using 440 GeV proton beams and at M3, UNILAC, at GSI, using 1.1 GeV U ions.

The energy stored in actual and future accelerators is potentially destructive for the accelerator equipment having direct interaction with high energy particles. High energetic beams may interact with several components present in particle accelerators, so it is of primary importance to predict the extension of the possible damage.

In general, in case of interaction between a high energy particle beam and a material, different response regimes may occur. This depends on several parameters, mainly the deposited energy, the energy density, the interaction duration and the material strength [1]. The first possibility is the case in which the induced stress waves and the vibrations remain in the elastic domain. In this case the deposited energy density is low, typically below 100 J cm^{-3} , the changes in density are negligible and the stress waves travel in the material at the speed of sound. On the other hand, for medium energy levels, between 100 and 10000 J cm^{-3} , the stress waves are generated in the plastic domain. This implies the velocity of the waves is lower than the elastic domain speed and there are permanent deformations in the component, also once the load is over. The last case implies that a large amount of energy is delivered on the component. In the matter there is the initiation of shock-waves, in which there is a nearly discontinuous change in the characteristic of the medium (pressure, temperature and density). The discontinuity moves with a supersonic velocity and this makes the mass transport phenomenon to become relevant. Besides, in the material close to the hit zone the encountered temperatures are very high and two possible situations can arise. If the energy deposition is very rapid, such that the deposition time is shorter than the system hydrodynamic characteristic time, the material density remains near its normal density (isochoric transformation). Nevertheless, the temperature and the pressure increase and reach very high values. Once the hydrodynamic rarefaction process starts, the material can expand reaching lower values of density and pressure. This last pattern is also found in case of slow energy deposition process: the material reaches directly a condition characterized by low pressure and density because the hydrodynamic characteristic time is faster than the energy deposition rate.

In the case of LHC, different thermal loads must be taken into account depending on the interaction condition. In normal situations, a continuous interaction provokes a constant energy-rate deposition over a long period (from some second up to few hours). In this case thermal stresses and deformations take place, but no dynamic response can usually be observed. Otherwise, in case of abnormal beam impacts, energy is rapidly deposited in time-scales of the order of microseconds or nanoseconds. This load condition typically entails a dynamic response of the structure. The resulting thermal stresses and deformations may affect the integrity or the proper functionality of the hit equipment. It is hence clear that in-depth thermo-mechanical analyses are fundamental.

Additionally, regardless of the type of mechanical response, the incident particles could cause radiation damage by displacing many atoms from their lattice sites by collisions, thereby creating vacancies and self-interstitial atoms. They might cluster, forming interstitial and vacancy dislocation loops or vacancy stacking-fault tetrahedra, or they can diffuse to dislocations, or to other defect sinks such as grain boundaries. The loops and small clusters that remain in the lattice act as obstacles to dislocation motion and raise the stress required for yield and subsequent plastic flow. Also, other physical properties (i.e. electrical and thermal conductivity) are usually affected by the radiation-induced structural changes and need to be investigated.

2. Long-term irradiation effects in materials for HL-LHC collimators

2.1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATIONS

As introduced before, the interaction of radiation with materials induces microscopic changes that affect their thermo-mechanical and electrical properties [2]. The radiation-induced damage can be quantified by means of two quantities:

- Displacement per atoms (dpa): it represents how often an atom is displaced on average during the irradiation, because of the displacement cascade generated by the scattering of the incoming particle by a nucleus [2]
- Transmutation gases: inelastic collision of highly energetic hadrons can generate nuclei with a different atomic number in the material, including gases as hydrogen and helium [3].

In particle accelerators, the beam intercepting devices are exposed to beam, and thus their functionality may be affected by radiation damage [4][5]. In this work, we focus on the beam-intercepting devices (BIDs) family, and we thus study a range of materials currently installed in some BIDs, or envisaged for future upgrades.

A special attention is given to molybdenum-carbide graphite (MoGr) composite, as this material, in view of its low electrical resistivity compared to other C-based composite, has been chosen as absorber for the new collimators of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN [6][7]. In view of the High-Luminosity upgrade of the Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC), new low-impedance collimators will be indeed installed to avoid beam instabilities [8][9].

In the LHC, two counteracting proton beams at 7 TeV are circulating. The unique radiation environment created by the 7 TeV protons cannot be reproduced elsewhere. For this reason, the radiation hardness of candidate materials for collimators must be evaluated in a different way and in alternative facilities. One of the most promising solution to test materials is ion irradiation. The residual activation induced by low energy (some MeV) is very low, and this simplifies the post-irradiation examination both in term of time and cost [10][11][11] dpa is proportional to this quantity [12] in a small penetration of particle in the materials, and this aspect must be taken into account during the post-irradiation examination. During ion irradiation at energies lower than Coulomb barrier, there is no production of He and H gases by nuclear reactions. For high energy particles

irradiation transmutation gases are additionally interacting with displacement-induced defects, and they can influence the macroscopic response of materials [2]

The results presented in the following sections refer to the irradiation campaign performed in 2019 at the M-Branch of the UNILAC accelerator at GSI. The experiment was carried out using ^{48}Ca ions with an energy of 4.8 MeV/u. Prior to the test, the dpa along the ion track is calculated with Monte-Carlo based simulation with the use of FLUKA [13][14][15]. Materials samples were irradiated at different ion fluences to study the degradation of properties as a function of the dpa. The thermo-mechanical design of the sample holders was also studied to predict the maximum temperature and stresses expected in the samples during the irradiation. The experimental design and simulations are presented elsewhere [16][17].

In this experimental campaign, a new grade of MoGr produced by Nanoker, Spain (Nb-8304Ng) was tested for the first time. This material is currently installed in 12 collimators, ready to operate in the HL-LHC. Eight out of 12 of these collimators are also equipped with coated MoGr blocks, to further decrease the electrical resistivity. This metal coating is also tested for the first time under irradiation.

For sake of comparison, two grades of MoGr (Nb-8304Ng by Nanoker, MG-6541Fc by Brevetti Bizz, Italy), one grade of CFC (FS140 by Tatsuno/Across, Japan) and one of polycrystalline isotropic graphite (R4550 by SGL, Germany) were irradiated. Molybdenum coatings were produced by two different sputtering techniques: conventional DC magnetron sputtering (DCMS) [18] and high-power impulse magnetron sputtering (HiPIMS) [19].

In this work, we focus on the electrical resistivity and on the microscopic analysis of the irradiated materials.

The electrical resistivity is one of the key properties of collimators absorbers, therefore special attention should be paid to its degradation induced by the defects cumulated during long-term irradiation. The electrical resistivity is measured with the four-probe methods, with a custom-built measurement set-up. As previously underlined, the ions penetrate only the first tens of microns, and this must be considered when measuring. The resistivity of the irradiated layer is calculated by assuming a parallel resistor model composed by a uniform irradiated layer, and the unirradiated bulk. For the coated samples, three layers are considered. The details of the measurement are explained elsewhere [20][17].

Some microscopic analyses were also performed to understand the changes in electrical resistivity. Raman spectroscopy test are carried out for graphite-based materials, while the coatings are analysed by means of a SEM-FIB apparatus.

2.2 GRAPHITE-BASED MATERIALS

2.2.1 Evolution of electrical resistivity

In Figure 1, the evolution of the electrical resistivity as a function of the average dpa is shown. For all the graphitic materials, the resistivity is increasing as a function of the dpa. In terms of absolute resistivity value, the two MoGr grades remain below the CFC and graphite up to a dpa of $3 \cdot 10^{-4}$. At higher dpa, the MoGr Nb8304Ng approaches the resistivity value of graphite.

Figure 1: Electrical resistivity of the four bulk materials as a function of the average dpa in the irradiated layer.

The initial resistivity of these materials is however very different, and it is thus interesting to observe its evolution normalized to the non-irradiated value, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Normalized electrical resistivity as a function of the average dpa.

2.2.2 Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy is a valid technique to detect microstructural defects of graphite crystal, and it is thus useful to analyse the radiation-induced changes. One of the most investigated features is the ratio between the so-called D (the peak at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the G bands (the peak at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$). These parameters are related to the in-plane crystalline order of the graphite crystal: the higher the ration between G and D peaks, the more ordered are the graphite crystallites [21][22][23].

The penetration depth of the laser used for the analysis is around 40-100 nm [24][25][26], and it thus acquiring the response of the first irradiated layer. The average dpa rate in the volume investigated with the Raman spectroscopy is constant and it ranges around $1.2\text{-}1.4 \cdot 10^{-5}\text{ dpa/h}$.

In Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 5, and Figure 6, the spectra of the four graphitic materials irradiated at different dpa are shown. An increase of the D peak intensity, and a small shift to a higher frequency is detected. It is also interesting to observe that, at the maximum dpa, the D peak in MoGr Nb8304Ng develops a shoulder. This feature is not detected in other materials, but it is found in literature for ion-irradiated highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) [27][28].

The G and D peaks remain well separated. The tendency to form a single asymmetric peak is related to amorphization [24]: this can be therefore excluded for these samples. In the spectra of graphite, CFC and MoGr MG6541Fc, the fitting of the first-order band requires the introduction of an additional peak at $\sim 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This peak has been related to the presence of interstitial atoms involved in sp^3 -like bonds between adjacent basal planes [29][30].

Figure 3: Raman spectra evolution for MoGr Nb8304Ng for different levels of dpa.

Figure 4: Raman spectra evolution for graphite R4550 for different levels of dpa.

Figure 5: Raman spectra evolution for CFC FS140 for different levels of dpa.

Figure 6: Raman spectra evolution for MoGr MG6541Fc for different levels of dpa.

For a quantitative analysis, the spectra are fitted to obtain the relevant peak parameters. Figure 7 shows the increase of the peak intensity ratios I_D/I_G as a function of dpa. The ratio increases as a

function of the dpa for all the materials, and the two MoGr grades have a higher variation. These composites are characterized by a higher graphitized structure before irradiation.

Figure 7: Peak intensity ratios I_D/I_G as a function of the dpa.

The damage accumulation under irradiation is thus more relevant for materials with a higher degree of crystalline order. Figure 8 shows the normalized ratios I_D/I_G as a function of I_D/I_G before irradiation at the highest dpa ($3 \cdot 10^{-4}$). The graph indicates that there is an exponential decrease of the observed damage as a function of the initial disorder level in the structure.

Figure 8: Peak intensity ratios ID/IG normalized for their pristine value as a function of their initial values at the highest dpa.

It is important to understand if this corresponds to a higher number of defects that are retained in the graphitic matrix. According to the dislocation-accumulation model [31], the I_D/I_G ratio is proportional to the square root of the radiation-induced vacancy in HOPG.

The microstructure of HOPG is, as much as a single graphite crystal, characterized by the absence of the D peak. For the materials presented in this analysis, it is important to exclude the contribution of the defects already present in the lattice, which is therefore subtracted from the irradiated value to highlight only the contribution of the radiation-induced defects. In Figure 9, the incremental change of I_D/I_G as a function of the dpa is shown and compared to the HOPG data found in literature. From these data, it is possible to conclude that the defects accumulation in the materials is similar. At this level of dpa, the initial microstructure plays a minor role. In particular, the contribution of pre-existing defects, such as grain boundaries, is not relevant in absorbing the radiation-induced defects [17].

Figure 9: Incremental increase of the I_D/I_G ratio as a function of the dpa for the materials presented in this work. As a comparison, the effect of ion irradiation on HOPG is taken from [31].

2.2.3 Thermal annealing

The crystal lattice after irradiation is characterized by different types of defects. Depending on the irradiation conditions and on the material properties, point defects (vacancies or interstitials), cluster of point defects, line, planar and volume defects can be found in the crystal. This configuration can be modified by heating the material, and thus activating diffusion processes. When the temperature allows overcoming the activation energy Q for defect diffusion, they become mobile, and they interact between themselves. Vacancies and interstitials can either recombine or migrate to crystal boundaries, where they self-annihilate. The diffusion of defects can, however, also facilitate their clustering. If the defects annihilation is relevant, a recovery of the initial crystal order is possible.

Raman spectroscopy is performed after heating the samples at different temperatures, and the I_D/I_G ratio is analysed to study the evolution of the concentration of defects.

Figure 10 presents the evolution of the I_D/I_G ratio as a function of temperature for two samples of MoGr irradiated at different dpa. It is interesting to notice that for the sample irradiated at the lowest dpa the pristine value of I_D/I_G is recovered after a thermal treatment at 200-250 °C, while at higher dpa a temperature of 350 °C is needed. This behaviour might indicate the formation of more stable and complex defects at higher dpa.

Figure 10: Evolution of the I_D/I_G as a function of temperature for MoGr Nb8304Ng samples irradiated at different dpa levels.

Figure 11 represents the same evolution for graphite R4550. The temperatures needed for a complete recovery of the pristine structure are, however, lower: the small increase of I_D/I_G observed at low dpa is, in fact, already recovered at 100 °C, while for the higher dpa a temperature of 250 °C is needed to approach the pristine value.

In both cases, the temperature annihilation temperature is much lower with respect to the expected recrystallization temperature of graphite (>1500°C). The annealing of graphite below 300 °C is generally assigned to a mutual recombination of intimate Frenkel pairs defects [32].

Figure 11: Evolution of the I_D/I_G as a function of temperature for graphite R4550 samples irradiated at different dpa levels.

2.3 METALLIC COATINGS

2.3.1 Evolution of electrical resistivity

In Figure 12, the electrical resistivity as a function of the dpa for four coating materials is shown. The increase of resistivity of all the coatings produced with HIPIMS is not proportional to the dpa. The Mo coating produced with DCMS technique presents instead a relevant increase starting from a dpa of $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

Figure 12: Electrical resistivity of the coating materials investigated as a function of the dpa.

Figure 13 shows the normalized increase of the electrical resistivity as a function of dpa. The coating produced with HIPIMS presents a maximum increase of electrical resistivity between 2-4, but there is not a visible trend as a function of the dpa.

Figure 13: Normalized electrical resistivity of the coating materials investigated as a function of the dpa.

2.3.2 Microscopic investigation

The microscopy investigation of the metallic coating after irradiation is carried out with the use of a SEM-FIB microscope. The results presented here refer to the coating irradiated at the maximum dpa ($1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ dpa), which corresponds to the expected damage level in the coatings at the end of the HL-LHC era in the most loaded secondary collimators.

The aim of this analysis is to ensure that the observed increase of resistivity is not related to fracture or to partial detachment of the coating from the substrate. This event should in fact be avoided in the machine, to avoid contamination to the UHV environment.

Figure 14 shows the HIPIMS Mo coating on MoGr Nb8304Ng. The columnar and dense structure is preserved and there are no macroscopic defects. The adhesion to the substrate is also ideal as before irradiation.

Figure 14: Microstructure of HIPIMS Mo-coating on MoGr NB8304Ng irradiated at the maximum dpa (10^{-3}).

The same considerations apply to the HIPIMS Mo coating on graphite, as shown in Figure 15; some porosities close to the interface cannot be ascribed to radiation damage, as this feature is also visible in non-irradiated materials, in correspondence of surface irregularities of the graphite substrate.

Figure 15: Microstructure of HIPIMS Mo-coating on Gr R4550 irradiated at the maximum dpa (10^{-3}).

In Figure 16, the microstructure of the Mo coating produced by DCMS is presented. This coating is characterized by porosities already before irradiation, which can explain the higher electrical resistivity before irradiation [20].

Figure 16: Microstructure of DCMS Mo-coating on MoGr Mg6541Fc irradiated at the maximum dpa (10^{-3}).

Figure 17: Microstructure of HIPIMS Cu-coating on MoGr NB8304Ng irradiated at the maximum dpa (10^{-3}).

Finally, in Figure 17, the Cu coating is shown. Here, as well, there are no changes in the coating morphology.

All the investigated coatings do not show any visible defects after irradiation. The changes in the resistivity could be therefore related to electron scattering by point-defects.

It is worth recalling that the Mo coating produced by DCMS has a higher resistivity before irradiation, and it is also presenting a sharper increase of resistivity, starting from a dpa of $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

Before irradiation, this coating presents bigger grain size with respect to the one produced with HIPIMS, but a worst connection between them. It is well reported in literature that the grain boundaries act as sinks for point defects [33]. The HIPIMS coating presents a higher number of boundaries, which can therefore absorb a higher number of defects and minimize the increase of resistivity.

The HIPIMS Mo-coating, which is currently installed in the secondary collimators, seems therefore to have a good radiation resistance and the maximum expected increase of resistivity is compatible with the technical specification [34]. It is however important to mention that the effect of gas production is not included in this analysis, but it must be assessed with proton irradiation [35].

3. Short term irradiation: thermomechanical dynamic effects

The introduction at CERN of new extremely energetic particle accelerators, such as the high-luminosity large hadron collider (HL-LHC) or the proposed future circular collider (FCC), will increase the energy stored in the circulating particle beams by almost a factor of two (from 360 to 680 MJ) and of more than 20 (up to 8500 MJ), respectively. In this scenario, it is paramount to assess the dynamic thermomechanical response of materials presently used, or being developed for future use, in beam intercepting devices (such as collimators, targets, dumps, absorbers, spoilers, windows, etc.) exposed to potentially destructive events caused by the impact of energetic particle beams. For this reason, two HiRadMat experiments, named MultiMat-1 and MultiMat-2, with the goal of assessing the behaviour of samples exposed to high-intensity, high-energy proton pulses, made of a broad range of materials relevant for collimators and beam intercepting devices, thin film coatings and advanced equipment.

At the UNILAC accelerator at GSI, 100 μs long ^{238}U ions beam pulses were impacting various thin targets. The dynamic response and the beam-induced temperature increase were monitored using Laser Doppler Vibrometry and infrared thermography respectively. The target surface velocities corresponding to beam impact-induced stress waves were simulated using the Ansys code. The effect of beam radiation damage induced material hardening was monitored up to fluences of 3×10^{13} i/cm^2 and the corresponding elastic modulus was fitting the values measured by microindentation on irradiated materials.

This section describes the experiment and its main results, collected online thanks to an extensive acquisition system and after the irradiation by non-destructive examination, as well as the numerical simulations performed to benchmark experimental data and extend materials constitutive models.

3.1 MULTIMAT-1

3.1.1 Test bench

The Multimatt-1 test-bench consisted in a leak-tight aluminium vessel hosting 16 target stations, each one-meter long, mounted on a rotatable barrel allowing to bring each station into impact position (Figure 18) [36].

Figure 18. Multimot-1 setup, with a zoom of the Geneva mechanism adopted to rotate the barrel hosting the different lines of specimens.

Figure 19. The actuation system of the Multimot-1 experiment.

Each target station hosted a variable number of material slender bars supported at the two extremities on graphite restraints, with pressed contact granted by springs, as shown in Figure 20. The samples tested in the experiment had cross sections ranging from $8 \times 8 \text{ mm}^2$ to $12 \times 11.5 \text{ mm}^2$ and lengths of 120 mm or 247 mm. These geometries allowed disentangling relevant phenomena, namely, power deposition, axial wave propagation, flexural oscillations and heat diffusion. These mechanical and thermal effects were acquired in real time with strain gauges and thermal probes directly mounted on the samples.

Figure 20. Schematic representation of a Multimot-1 target line with its sample supports.

A radiation-hard camera was mounted on the side of the vessel to allow observations of the impacted specimens immediately after each pulse. The top viewport was instead designed to allow the use of a Laser Doppler Vibrometer (LDV) system to acquire in real time the beam-induced vibrations of the samples (Figure 21). Each of the viewports featured an optically-transparent, temperature and radiation resistant window, designed to withstand possible impacts of fragments ejected by the irradiated specimens. Finally, the vessel was equipped with windows, made of beryllium and carbon fibre-reinforced carbon (CFC) at the beam entry and exit ports to minimize the interaction with the particle beam, ensuring at the same time leak tightness and structural resistance.

Figure 21. Radiation-hard camera (a) and LDV (b) installed on the Multimot-1 setup.

3.1.2 Material samples

The tested materials encompass composites and coating of interest for BID, already described in previous chapters. Additional light materials such as carbon foams, thermal pyrolytic graphite (TPG) and honey-cell 3D printed titanium were tested, together with dense materials of interest for particle beam absorbers (copper-diamond REF, tantalum, tungsten and molybdenum alloys). A summary of the materials in the scope of Multimot-1 is given in Table 1.

Table 1. The materials tested in MultiMat-1.

#	Material	Density [g/cm ³]	Coating	#	Material	Density [g/cm ³]	Coating
1	Inermet180	18.0		10	MG6530Aa	2.50	2µm Cu
2	Ta10W	16.9		11	MG6541Fc	2.49	8µm Mo
3	Ta2.5W	16.7		12	TPG	2.26	
4	TZM	10.0		13	TG1100	2.19	
5	CuCD-G2	5.40		14	R4550	1.90	2µm Cu
6	CuCD-G1	5.40		15	CFC AC150K	1.88	8µm Mo
7	SiC	3.21		16	Ti6Al4V	1.62	
8	MG6403Fc	2.54	5µm TiN	17	CFOAM	0.40	
9	NNK265-266	2.52		18	Al6082-T651	2.70	

3.1.3 Experiment parameters

Specimens were submitted to three different types of impacts: transversally-centred impacts, intermediate transversal offset and, where a coating was present, grazing impacts (Figure 22).

Figure 22. MultiMat-1 impact positions: centred a), off-axis b) and grazing c).

After impacts with high-intensity pulses, material lines were first brought into cool-down position, where a direct argon flow lowered their temperature, and then in inspection position, with the rad-hard camera spanning the overall length of the lines, thus allowing to visually check the status of the impacted specimens (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Schematic representation of the interior of the MultiMat-1 aluminium tank: the beam collision position, the active cooling station and the inspection position are shown.

The Multimot-1 experiment featured pulses of intensity ranging from one to 288 proton bunches and average bunch intensity of about 1.2×10^{11} protons per bunch (p/b), beam size between 0.25 mm and of 2 mm, as shown in Table 2. The intensity of the implemented beam pulses was progressively increased during the test, reaching energy densities U_{max} up to 10^4 J cm⁻³.

Table 2. Beam parameters during the Multimot-1 test run: number of delivered pulses P , number of bunches per pulse b , average intensity I , beam size σ . A total of 478 pulses (2.25×10^{15} p) were shot from 2 to 17/10/2017.

Material	P #	b	I [10^{11} p/b]	σ [mm]	Material	P #	b	I [10^{11} p/b]	σ [mm]
IT180	9	1-24	1.1	2	MG6530Aa	46	1-288	1.3	0.25, 0.5
Ta10W	7	1-24	1.2	2	MG6541Fc	42	1-288	1.3	0.25, 0.5
Ta2.5W	7	1-24	1.2	2	TPG	21	1-24	1.1	2
TZM	50	1-36	1.3	0.5, 2	TG1100	28	1-288	1.3	0.25, 0.5
CuCD-G2	30	1-24	1.1	0.5, 2	R4550	47	1-288	1.2	0.25, 0.5
CuCD-G1	17	1-24	1.4	0.5	CFC-AC150K	32	1-288	1.2	0.25, 0.5
SiC	81	1-24	1.1	0.5, 2	Ti6Al4V	9	1-24	1.1	2
MG6403Fc	40	1-288	1.3	0.25, 0.5	CFOAM	8	144 - 288	1.2	0.25, 0.5
NNK265-266	28	1-288	1.3	0.25, 0.5	Al6082-T651	8	24 - 72	1.1	2

The specimen aspect ratio allowed generating signals in which the footprint of different phenomena, at distinct timescales, could be easily detected. In the first $1 \div 10$ μ s, a signal rise time, associated to the pulse duration, occurred: in this phase, the highest strain rates were attained, with values as high as 10^4 s⁻¹; transversal waves were also excited, with periods of several microseconds; these were particularly appreciable in those materials having slow transverse speed of sound, such as anisotropic materials. Subsequently, an axial wave, with a period in the order of 100 μ s, was generated: this regime proved to be particularly useful to study material elastic constants, internal damping and axial strength. In case of off-centre beam impacts, bending oscillations were additionally induced: these had a period in the range of 1 ms and were useful to determine the flexural strength, plasticity and low-frequency damping. Finally, temperature evolved on a significantly longer timescale, 0.1 s or more for the considered dimensions: this is why most of the dynamic phenomena could be reasonably considered as quasi-instantaneous and adiabatic.

3.1.4 Results

CFC. Figure 24a shows the temperature profile induced over the 4th sample (the most loaded one, see Figure 25) of the CFC AC150K line at the end of an impact with a 36 bunches-pulse, intensity 1.24×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 0.5$ mm. A maximum temperature of about 114°C is reached at the end of the energy deposition time, i.e. $\tau = 900$ ns, decreasing to $T_f = 38.1$ °C after about 2 s and then remaining almost constant, as no convection was considered in the simulation.

A comparison with the experimental temperature reported in Figure 24b, reveals a peak of temperature of $T_{peak} = 33.1$ °C after 1.7 s, in acceptable agreement with the numerical simulation, particularly taking into account the thermal impedance between the Pt100 probe and the sample as well as the convection (natural and/or forced). The subsequent temperature decrease is due to the argon-based cooling system installed in the experiment. This result confirms the accuracy of the values of specific heat c_p in temperature implemented in the simulations.

Figure 24. The temperature field over the 4th CFC AC150k specimen impacted by a 36 bunches-pulse with bunch intensity of 1.24×10^{11} p/b, $\sigma = 0.5$ mm and 2.7 mm x-wise offset (a); a comparison between the experimental and the (minimum) simulated temperature acquired at the midpoint of its bottom face is also shown (b).

Figure 25. The power distribution over the four CFC AC150K samples (see Table 3) due to a 36 bunches-pulse with bunch intensity of 1.24×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 0.5$ mm.

The transverse (i.e. along the direction normal to basal planes, or x according to the specimens layout reported in Fig. 19) and longitudinal total strains induced by a 288 bunch-pulse are shown in Figure 26. A very close agreement between numerical and experimental data is found both in terms of amplitude and of frequencies (16.3 kHz and 66.7 kHz for the experimental longitudinal and transverse strains, 16.4 kHz and 70.5 kHz for their numerical counterparts, respectively).

Figure 26. The numerical and experimental longitudinal (a) and transverse (b), i.e., normal to basal planes, total strains acquired on the 4th CFC AC150K sample subject to a centred 288 bunches-pulse with intensity 1.27×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 0.5$ mm.

A Rayleigh damping ratio of $\zeta = 0.001\%$ at 65 kHz was also found for transverse strains. As expected, transverse strains assume values which are much larger than the longitudinal strains, this being due to both a larger CTE in the x direction ($\sim 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ vs. $\sim 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$) and a smaller Young’s modulus (3.1 GPa vs. 110.2 GPa). It is worth remarking that the longitudinal strains are, in fact, negative, as AC150K has a negative CTE in the axial direction. This means that the quasi-instantaneous heat deposition associated to the impact makes the specimen willing to shrink in that direction, being prevented to do so by inertia, resulting then in a state of tension. This is confirmed by simulations: Figure 27a shows that during the 288 bunches-pulse, the impacted portion of the specimen is in tension, while compression occurs in the outer regions of the sample.

Figure 27. The longitudinal mechanical strain occurring after a 288-bunch pulse impacting a CFC AC150K sample (a) and a MoGr NN265-266 sample (b).

Molybdenum-Graphite.

A more canonical behaviour than the one observed for CFC AC150K is found for the first MoGr NNK265-266 sample. In this case, in fact, the centered 288 bunches-pulse with 1.23×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 0.5$ mm provokes a state of compression about the sample axis during the impact, while the surrounding areas experience tension, as clearly visible in Figure 27b. Two tensile waves then rise at

the free end faces of the NNK265-266 sample in order to fulfil the boundary conditions in the longitudinal direction, then propagating towards the opposite face and superimposing along the specimen's length, as shown in Figure 28a. Here a close correlation is found between simulated and actual longitudinal total strains acquired at the midpoint of the right surface of the specimen, with a numerical value of the longitudinal wave frequency of 22.5 kHz, against an experimental value of 21.8 kHz. Also in this case a linear elastic constitutive model was implemented, with a Rayleigh damping ratio of $\zeta = 0.0075\%$ found at 22.5 kHz.

Figure 28. The longitudinal total strain occurring on the first NNK265-266 sample impacted by a 288 bunches-pulse with intensity 1.23×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 0.5$ mm (a). The measured and simulated maximum temperature over time for the same 288 bunches-pulse and for a 36 bunches-pulse impacting the second NNK265-266 sample.

Figure 28b shows the variations in time of the maximum temperature occurring on the second NNK265-266 sample of line 12. for the 288-bunch pulse and for a less intense 36-bunch pulse. The second NNK265-266 samples is analysed as no temperature probe survived to the impacts on the first one. From the plot it can be observed that a considerable difference exists between numerical and experimental values already for the 36-bunches pulse. This deviation becomes even larger for the case of the impact with 288 bunches: here the measured temperatures exceed 155°C , which is the specified limit temperature for the adhesive bonding the probe to the sample. The good matching between numerical predictions and strain measurements seems to point to a strong underestimation of the temperature measure, possibly due a partial detachment of the sensor from the surface of the sample.

As found for CFC AC150K, also for MoGr transverse strains assume values that are much larger than their longitudinal counterpart. This can be easily observed in Figure 29a, where the numerical total transverse strains induced by a 288-bunches pulse in the most loaded samples of different MoGr grades and in CFC samples are reported for the sake of comparison. Differences between MoGr grades are essentially due to the variations in the transversal CTE between them. The lower total strain in CFC is due to the significantly lower energy deposited on this material.

Figure 29b shows also the mechanical strains, proportional to thermal stresses, probed at the midpoint of the lateral faces of the samples.

Figure 29. Simulated transverse total strains (a) occurring on the core of the most loaded sample of various MoGr grades (NNK265-266, MG6403Fc and MG6530Aa) and of CFC AC150K impacted by a 288-bunch pulse with average intensity of 1.25×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 0.5$ mm; the numerical mechanical strains arising on the lateral faces of the same samples are shown in (b).

Graphite. The longitudinal total strain acquired on the outer surface of the most loaded R4550 sample impacted by a centred 288 bunches-pulse having average intensity of 1.25×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 0.5$ mm sigma is shown in Figure 30a. A deviation between numerical and experimental data is observed in terms of amplitude and frequency: a subsequent 6% reduction of the Young’s modulus implemented in the considered linear elastic constitutive law, allowed achieving a better correlation. Moreover, a Rayleigh damping ratio of $\zeta = 3 \%$ was implemented.

Observing Figure 30a, it is possible to notice that in R4550 longitudinal strain waves feature a quite regular step-like shape, with minor effects due to coupling with radial waves. In fact, the simulated dynamic component of the total transverse strain shown in Figure 30b is small, the overall strain oscillating slightly about its static value. This behaviour is due to the fact that the energy deposition time $\tau = 7.95 \mu\text{s}$ is very close to the radial waves propagation period $\Gamma_r = 7.88 \mu\text{s}$. In this condition, stress relaxation in transverse direction takes place while energy is still being deposited, leading to a significant reduction of the dynamic component of transverse stresses. This dynamic component of stress is however expected to fully develop in larger cross-sections, such as in a collimator jaw, having longer transverse wave periods.

Figure 30. The longitudinal total strains (a) occurring on the outer surface of the most loaded R4550 sample impacted by 288 bunches of intensity 1.25×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 0.5$ mm. The undamped numerical longitudinal and transverse total strains are shown in (b).

Copper-Diamond. The case of CuCD-G1 line impacted by a 1-bunch pulse having intensity of 1.43×10^{11} protons, $\sigma = 0.5$ mm sigma and an offset of 3.1 mm in x-direction is analyzed on the most loaded sample. As additional mean of comparison, an elasto-plastic model based on the measures carried out for a similar CuCD grade (namely, CuCD 40/60) [37] was also implemented. Figure 31a and Figure 31b show the propagation of longitudinal waves through the midpoint of the bottom face of the sample: while the elastic model seems to better match the experimental period, on the other hand the elasto-plastic counterpart appears to be able to mimic the amplitude of the higher frequency content of the signal. The bending oscillations associated to the same pulse are shown in Figure 31c and Figure 31d. In the former, a comparison between the purely elastic and elasto-plastic models with respect the experimental data is provided, while the latter reports the numerical results with the addition of damping in the elasto-plastic case. A Rayleigh $\zeta = 8\%$ damping ratio is also introduced, estimated via logarithmic decrement from the experimental flexural oscillations [38].

Figure 31. The longitudinal total strain occurring on the second sample of the CuCD-G1 line impacted by a 1 bunch-pulse with intensity 1.43×10^{11} p, $\sigma = 0.5$ mm and an x-wise offset of 3.1 mm with respect to the sample's axis. The strain associated to the propagation of longitudinal waves is shown for the case of a linear-elastic (a) and elasto-plastic (b) constitutive model. Flexural oscillations are shown instead in (c) and (d).

TaW, Inermet180, TZM and SiC. The first sample of the TaW line (i.e. a Ta10W made specimen), given the material's density, results to be the most loaded one when impacted by a 2-bunches pulse having intensity of 2.19×10^{11} p/b, $\sigma = 2$ mm sigma and an x-wise offset of 2.2 mm with respect to the

sample axis, resulting into a maximum beam-induced ΔT of about 380 °C. The longitudinal total strain at the middle of the sample bottom face is shown in Figure 32a: the numerical response is obtained via a purely elastic constitutive law. The propagation of a classical step-shaped axial wave can be clearly seen. A good agreement between experimental and numerical results is noticeable both in terms of amplitudes and frequency content (6.6 kHz vs 7.1 kHz for the simulated response). The effects of a subsequent 24 bunches-pulse impacting the same sample are shown in Figure 32b: a clear plasticization of the specimen is visible. The planned post-mortem tests, as tomography, which are currently ongoing on the impacted specimens, will allow gaining further insight about their state of integrity.

Figure 32. The simulated longitudinal total strains occurring at the midpoint of the bottom face of a Ta10W sample impacted by a 2-bunches pulse with intensity of 2.19×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 2$ mm (a); the plastic deformation induced by a subsequent 24 bunches-pulse impacting the same sample is shown in (b).

Similar investigations are performed for the first Inermet180 sample. Given a density of 18 g/cm^3 , this sample is the most loaded of its line when impacted by a 1-bunch pulse having intensity of 2.03×10^{11} p/b, $\sigma = 2$ mm sigma and x-wise offset of -3 mm with respect to the sample axis, inducing a maximum ΔT of about 206 °C. The longitudinal total strain at the middle of the sample bottom face is shown in Figure 33a: the numerical response is obtained via an elasto-plastic constitutive law. Good correlation between experimental and numerical results is observable both in terms of amplitudes and frequency content (9.1 kHz vs 9.3 kHz for the simulated response). The amplitude of high frequency content in the axial response, mainly due to radial wave propagation, is larger in the simulated response. For this reason, a Raleigh damping ratio of $\zeta = 1\%$ associated to the frequency of radial waves is adopted: in this case, however, the numerical signal seems to be too much damped with respect its experimental counterpart, suggesting that an actual damping value smaller than 1% is present. As done for Ta10W, also here a clear plasticization of the specimen due to higher-intensity pulses is reached, as visible in Figure 33b.

Figure 33. The simulated longitudinal total strains occurring on midpoint of the bottom face of an IT180 sample impacted by a 1-bunch pulse with intensity of 2.03×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 2$ mm (a); the plastic deformation induced by subsequent 12 and 24 bunches-pulses impacting the same sample is shown in (b).

In fact, also the failure of different specimens was clearly observed during the experiment: this is the case of SiC and TZM samples, as shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34. The beam-induced failure of the second SiC sample of line 5 and of the second TZM sample of line 14, impacted by a 36 bunches-pulse with 1.18×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 0.5$ mm and by a 12-bunches pulse with 1.33×10^{11} p/b and $\sigma = 2$ mm, respectively.

Coatings. A series of grazing impacts were carried out on coated samples to probe the coatings strength, their adhesion to the substrates and to verify the extent of the induced surface damages in case of accidental scenarios. In this phase of the tests, energy deposition densities exceeded those associated to the HL-LHC BIE, by strongly focusing the beam, as shown in Table 3. Under these conditions, induced temperatures were expected to cause coating melting and ejection.

Table 3. Beam parameters of the most energetic pulses delivered during the MultiMat test run.

Material [Sub-Coat]	Intensity [10^{13} p]	Impact Parameter [μm]	$\sigma(x,y)$ [mm]
MG6541Fc- Mo	3.66	-150	0.29×0.31
MG6530 - Cu	3.99	-150	0.29×0.26
AC150K - Mo	3.68	-150	0.38×0.23
R4550 - Cu	4.04	-150	0.31×0.27

In order to correctly simulate such phenomena, the adoption of appropriate equations of state, strength and failure models would be required, together with the use of suitable explicit code. Nonetheless, preliminary thermal studies were carried out resorting to the ANSYS implicit solver in order to get a first approximation of the temperatures reached during the impacts. The smallest available nominal beam size of $\sigma = 0.25$ and the highest bunch intensity of 1.4×10^{11} p/b were implemented for the tests to mimic or, as it was the case. The samples were impacted 150 μm and 500 μm beneath the coated surface.

The effects of the pulses shot on coatings are shown in Figure 35, together with the beam parameters. As expected, it can be observed that copper-coated specimens exhibit a much more visible damage with respect to those samples which feature a coating in molybdenum, this being mainly due to copper lower melting temperature ($T_m^{Cu} = 1085$ °C vs. $T_m^{Mo} = 2623$ °C). Larger damage stripes (up to 1.9 mm) are therefore visible on Cu-coated samples, this also being due in part to the smaller impact factors implemented with respect to Mo-coated samples, as both 150 μm and 500 μm were considered for the latter, while only 150 μm were taken into account for the others.

Numerical simulations show that only a portion of the damage observable in Figure 35 are due to material melting. The case of MG6541Fc coated with Mo is presented in Figure 36: a maximum temperature of $T_{max}^{Mo} = 2845$ °C is found. In Figure 36a, the portion of the specimen undergoing temperatures higher than molybdenum melting temperature $T_m^{Mo} = 2623$ °C is shown in red: only 55.9 mm of the 120 mm-long damage stripe observed in Figure 35 experience melting, indicating that occurrence of micro-jetting and spallation in the remaining areas. A similar result is highlighted in Figure 36b, with a melted width of 0.32 mm out of the 1.31 mm found in Figure 35.

Figure 35. The effects of grazing pulses on Cu and Mo coatings, together with the implemented beam parameters.

Figure 36. The simulated grazing impact of a 288-bunch pulse with intensity $1.27 \times 10^{11} \text{ p/b}$ and $\sigma = 0.25 \text{ mm}$ over the molybdenum coating of a MG6541Fc sample. Melted portion of the coating are shown in red.

3.2 MULTIMAT-2

3.2.1 Goals

The Multimatt-1 experiment was a success under many aspects, allowing:

- The validation of materials and coatings adopted for the HL-LHC collimator prototypes
- The derivation of a robust strength model with damping for the graphitic materials, and refinement of the constitutive model of metals and CuCD
- The individuation of the failure mechanism for anisotropic graphitic materials, strongly dependent on longitudinal/transversal stress coupling

However, further objectives were still to be reached:

- The validation of materials and coatings adopted or envisaged for the HL-LHC collimator series production (and in particular, MoGr produced by Nanoker and HIPIMS coatings by DTI);
- The derivation of the strength model for the Nanoker MoGr;
- The characterization of a specific failure model for anisotropic graphitic materials, better characterizing the transversal stress domain;
- The testing of Nanoker CuCD up to 48 bunches, which represents the HL-LHC collimator accidental scenario (in Multimatt-1, CuCD was tested only up to 24 bunches).

For this reason, in 2020, a proposal was presented to the HiRadMat Scientific Board, with the idea of re-using the existing Multimatt-1 test bench, replacing the samples and improving the instrumentation, for a beam test in 2021. The proposal, which was endorsed by the Scientific Board, relied on the radioactive cooldown of the test bench, as it can be seen in Figure 37.

Figure 37. Decrease in time of the dose at contact in the Multimat-1 tank.

3.2.2 Experimental setup

The two key differences in Multimat-2 with respect to Multimat-1 were the following:

- Improved instrumentation, and in particular, strong increase of the transversal strain gauges on the anisotropic materials, to be able to capture and finely characterize the failure mode identified during Multimat-1 (Figure 29).
- Upgraded materials and coatings, with focus on the solutions adopted or envisaged for HL-LHC collimators (MoGr and graphite with and without coating, CuCD). Also, new solutions, such as CrGr and high-density MoGr were tested. Finally, a line has been dedicated to the testing of the strain gauges, and the characterization of the electromagnetic signal which disturbs the measurements in the first μ s after the beam passage.

Figure 38. A view on the CFC line in Multimot-2.

The Multimot-2 target stations are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Multimot-2 target lines.

#	Material	Density [g/cm ³]	Coating	#	Material	Density [g/cm ³]	Coating
1	MoGr 8304Ng	2.55	6µm Mo	5	Graphite R4550	1.85	2µm Cu
2	MoGr 8404Ng	2.57	6µm Mo	6	Graphite R4550	1.85	6µm Mo
3	MoGr high-ρ 2507Ng	2.70		7	CFC	1.67	
4	CrGr	2.30		8	CuCD Nanoker	5.40	

On top of these eight target stations, a ninth line was dedicated to the strain gauge characterization, and also included a steel target to generate a particle beam shower on the strain gauges.

The Multimot-2 experiment featured pulses of intensity ranging from one to 288 proton bunches. The bunch intensity, especially for the high energy shots, was this time limited by facility constraints to about 1×10^{11} protons per bunch (p/b). The beam size varied between 0.25 mm and 0.5 mm, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Beam parameters during the Multimot-2 test run: number of delivered pulses P , number of bunches per pulse b , average intensity I , beam size σ . A total of 275 pulses (7×10^{14} p) were shot from 20 to 13/09/2021.

Material	P #	b	σ [mm]	Material	P #	b	σ [mm]
MoGr 8304Ng	24	1-288	0.25, 0.5	Graphite Mo	28	1-288	0.25, 0.5
MoGr 8404Ng	46	1-288	0.25, 0.5	Graphite Cu	39	1-288	0.25, 0.5
MoGr 2507Ng	13	1-288	0.25, 0.5	CFC	42	1-288	0.25, 0.5
CrGr	16	1-288	0.25, 0.5	CuCD Nanoker	58	1-48	0.5

3.2.3 Preliminary results and planned PIE

At the moment of writing this report, the experiment has been completed since ten days. So far, it was possible to just perform a rapid visual inspection from outside the tank. Such inspection, combined with the online camera measurements, has not highlighted any visible failure in the tested materials. This in particular is an important result for CuCD (Figure 39), which in this experiment has been subjected, in its uncladded form, to unprecedented pulse intensity (up to 48 bunches, which represents the design scenario for HL-LHC collimators).

Figure 39. Top left and right: the two most loaded CuCD specimens (4th and 5th) before irradiation. Bottom left and right: the 4th and 5th specimen after irradiation. No evident change in the material state is observable.

For what concerns the coatings, results were similar to those obtained during Multimati-1, with the beam impact removing “stripes” with widths up to 2-3 mm from the material surface (Figure 40). This is not an issue for HL-LHC collimators, whose actuation allows, in case of a similar event, to move the tank parallel to the beam, exposing undamaged coated areas to the circulating protons.

Figure 40. Top: view of the 1st graphite sample, coated with copper. Bottom: zoom on the 1st graphite sample coated with molybdenum. In both cases, the beam impact ablates coating regions with width up to ~2 mm.

The test bench is currently in the HiRadMat cooldown area, waiting for the dose to go down enough to allow manipulation and post-irradiation examination. Examples of tests under consideration are:

- Impedance measurements to quantify the depletion of the coating impedance performances upon beam impact;
- Surface topography to measure the extent of surface damages induced by grazing shots;
- Tomography to ascertain the presence of internal damages in the impacted samples;
- Planarity to evaluate the occurrence of beam-induced plastic deformations (for metallic materials);
- Sigma test to measure the electric conductivity of samples
- Focused ion beam: an ion beam is used to mill the sample and to observe bulk-coating interface;
- Scratch test on coating to evaluate the quality of the bonding with the substrate after irradiation;
- SEM to analyse the internal microstructure of the samples;

- Thermo-physical / mechanical tests to evaluate changes in the physical/mechanical properties of samples.

3.3 DYNAMIC RESPONSE OF ISOTROPIC GRAPHITE IMPACTED BY U BEAM AT UNILAC, GSI – EFFECT OF RADIATION DAMAGE ACCUMULATION

In this section, the results of the online monitoring of bending and stress waves induced by 4.8 MeV/u U beams with a pulse duration of 100 μ s are described. With the set-up presented in Figure 41, the temperatures and the velocity at the rear side of thin discs during the impact of 4.8 MeV/u U ion beam -pulses could be recorded.

Figure 41: a) Sample holder with two graphite samples mounted above a luminescence screen b) schematic set-up for online monitoring of elastic waves on the rear side of the irradiated samples by a laser Doppler vibrometer. The temperature on both sample surfaces is monitored with a thermal camera. The experiments were conducted at the M3 beamline at UNILAC (from [40]).

To estimate the maximum temperature rise per pulse, it is assumed that the entire energy of a U-ion pulse is transformed into heat. For graphite this corresponds to a power density of 3 MW/cm³. This value was inserted in the ANSYS simulations continuously over the duration of the 100 μ s long ion pulse. The results of simulations of a quarter of a graphite disc with a diameter of 20 mm and a thickness of 0.5 mm are shown with a square beam spot of 1x1 cm², representative of simulations done for the different materials and geometries. Adiabatic boundary conditions were used justified by the short time scales of the involved processes. Figure 42a) shows the simulated temperature evolution of a single U ion- beam pulse on an isotropic graphite disc at different depths and radial positions. The temperature of the quasi-pristine sample increases during the duration of the pulse and reaches a maximum of 156 °C at the end of the ion pulse at 100 μ s in the centre of the beam spot ($y = 0, z = 0$). The generated heat is conducted through the sample equilibrating within 1 ms to almost

similar temperature values on both surfaces of the disc ($y = 0$, compare $z = 0$ and 0.5). Over the entire time the outer rim of the disc ($y = 10$, $z = 0$) remains at room temperature, confirming that the use of adiabatic conditions in the investigated time frame is adequate.

Figure 42: ANSYS simulated time dependent temperature evolution of a 0.5 mm thick isotropic graphite disc for 1 ms after the impact of a 100 μ s long U-ion pulse. a) pristine material b) thermal conductivity reduced to 4 W/m·K [39] in the material of the beam spot representing graphite after 4.8 MeV/u U ion- irradiation to a fluence of 3×10^{13} ions/cm² (from [40]).

To simulate the case of a radiation-damaged sample, the thermal conductivity of the volume exposed to the beam was reduced to 4 W/m·K [39]. The values of specific heat and coefficient of thermal expansion are expected to change towards those of glassy carbon. As the difference of both these properties is small between graphite and glassy carbon, they were kept constant in the simulation. Due to the degraded properties, the temperature at the sample surface ($y = 0$, $z = 0$) increases to 240 °C after a U-ion pulse of 100 μ s duration. A temperature of 255 °C is obtained if no heat conduction is included illustrating the severely limited heat conduction from the front of the sample within the time duration of the pulse. After 1 ms the temperature difference between the front and the back surface of the sample, at the central spot of the beam ($y = 0$, compare $z = 0$ and 0.5), is still larger than 50 °C. The achieved temperature evolutions were used as input for the mechanical simulations, shown in the subsequent chapters.

Figure 43a) and b) show velocity signals and corresponding fast Fourier transforms (FFTs) spectra measured with the LDV at the rear side of a 500 μ m thick SGL R6650 disc impacted with 4.8 MeV/u U ions-. The beam spot was a square with an area of 1x1 cm². For clarity, only data for the quasi-pristine sample as well as after the accumulation of a fluence of 1×10^{13} and 3.5×10^{13} ions/cm² are presented. In the pristine sample a harmonic oscillation with a frequency of 5.38 ± 0.02 kHz is generated in excellent agreement with the frequency $f_{b1,free}$ calculated for the free binding condition. With increasing U ion- fluence, the frequency signal increases to 6.10 ± 0.02 kHz at the maximum applied fluence of 3.5×10^{13} ions/cm². We ascribe the increase of the frequency to an increase of the Young's modulus in the irradiated area, assuming that the boundary conditions remained constant and no large failures of the samples such as cracks occurred. Irradiation of graphite results in the formation of interstitials and vacancies. Agglomeration of these defects creates vacancy clusters.

These defects prevent movement of dislocations and sliding of basal planes causing a significant hardening and increase of the Young's modulus.

Figure 43: a) Time dependent velocity signal measured by LDV and b) corresponding FFT spectra at the rear side of a free 0.5 mm thick isotropic R6650 graphite disc for the irradiation with 4.8 MeV/u Uions at different fluences. Corresponding ANSYS simulations: c) time dependent velocity and d) FFT spectra for the impact of a 100 μ s U-ions pulse (power density 3 MW/cm³). Depicted are simulations of a pristine sample and samples with values of Young modulus 2 and 3 times higher than the pristine value as well as thermal conductivity degradation from 95 W/m-K, (pristine graphite) to 11 W/m-K and 4 W/m-K-, respectively [1], in the heated volume (from [38]).

ANSYS simulations of the deformation of the graphite disc were performed to infer beam-induced changes of the Young's modulus. In a first step, the thermal input of Figure 42a) was used on a pristine disc. The velocity and the corresponding FFT spectrum in the centre of the rear side of the disc with free boundary conditions are shown in Figure 43c). An oscillation with a frequency of 5.32 ± 0.02 kHz is obtained, similar to the calculated value

In a second step, ANSYS simulations of discs with larger Young's modulus in the beam spot were conducted. In Figure 43c) and d) examples of the velocity in the centre of the rear side of discs with 2 and 3 times the pristine Young's modulus are shown. The properties of the part outside the beam spot were assumed to stay constant since the temperature increase is not high enough to significantly change the properties (as seen in Figure 42). The frequency spectra of the LDV recordings at different fluences can now be compared with the frequency results of the ANSYS simulations as demonstrated

in Figure 44a) for 2 and 3 times the pristine Young’s modulus. The frequencies for those two simulations were measured in the LDV signal at accumulated fluences of 1.5×10^{13} and 3.3×10^{13} ions/cm², respectively. The same procedure was used to estimate a continuous development of the Young’s modulus depending on the fluence as shown in Figure 44b).

To test the validity of this method, the deduced Young’s modulus values are compared to microindentation measurements on a sample series with different accumulated fluences. From the good agreement in the investigated fluence range it can be concluded that the LDV online measurements method provide realistic results for beam-induced changes of the Young’s modulus for isotropic graphite. This is excellent news, because it reduces the need to irradiate samples series with different accumulated fluences and avoids uncertainties due to property fluctuations between several samples.

Both methods show a large increase up to about 3 times the pristine Young’s modulus E_0 for irradiation with a fluence of 3×10^{13} U ions/cm². The obtained increase is similar to the ratio of the Young’s moduli of glassy carbon. This supports the assumption that intensive ion irradiation induces a transition towards a disordered structure similar to glassy carbon. Compared to neutron irradiation, the effects of swift heavy ion irradiation is much larger. The fluences achieved in this study correspond to less than 0.01 dpa as calculated by SRIM Kinchin and Pease damage calculation. Several tens of dpa are necessary for similar changes induced by neutron irradiation.

Figure 44: a) Measured bending frequency of isotropic SGL R6650 graphite as a function of 4.8 MeV/u U ion accumulated fluence. Shaded areas represent the frequencies obtained by ANSYS simulations with pristine properties as well as with 2 and 3 times the pristine Young’s modulus in the beam spot. The uncertainty of the frequencies of 0.02 kHz is obtained by the frequency resolution of the FFT. b) Relative increase of the Young’s modulus as a function of the U-ion fluence measured by microindentation and deduced from simulations of frequency shifts of LDV velocity signals. The shaded blue area represents the ratio of the Young’s modulus between the glassy carbon grade HTW Sigradur K and SGL R6650 taken from the data sheets (from [38]).

Besides the large amplitude caused by the bending of the sample, also elastic or plastic transversal stress waves are expected at a pulse length of 100 μ s and a deposited power of approximately 3 MW/cm³. These transversal waves propagate along the disk axis and appear in the MHz frequency regime. Time resolved frequency analysis of the LDV signal was performed by continuous wavelet transformation with a Morlet wavelet with a wave number of 20. The results for the first dynamic

response obtained for a pristine isotropic graphite target is shown in Figure 45. The highest wavelet coefficient appears at a frequency of 2.70 ± 0.02 MHz, very close to the calculated frequency of 2.73 MHz. This signal corresponds to an elastic stress wave as the pressure wave propagates at the speed of sound. The yield strength of graphite is not reached and no plastic deformation occurs. This supports our hypothesis that the sample properties outside the beam spot are not changed as inserted in the ANSYS simulations. The maximum of the wavelet coefficient is obtained at the end of the pulse of 100 μ s. At this point the highest values of temperature and velocity are reached, resulting in the highest thermal stress. After the end of the beam pulse the temperature difference decreases and the stress wave signal is rapidly damped.

Figure 45: a) Contour plot of the absolute wavelet coefficient as a function of time and frequency and maximum wavelet coefficient depending on the frequency. b) time dependent wavelet coefficient at 2.70 MHz. Both graphs show the impact of the first 4.8 MeV/u U-ion pulse on pristine isotropic graphite (from [38]).

4. Conclusions

In this document a broad range of analyses and studies performed on metallic, graphitic and diamond-based materials irradiated with proton beam at HiradMat, CERN and with ion beams at the GSI UNILAC facility were presented. Irradiated materials were selected as they are considered for use in beam intercepting devices in next generation accelerators .

Several important findings were highlighted, allowing to cast further light on the effects of swift heavy ions on these materials and allowing a valuable anticipation of the effects that high-energy particles in facilities as the HL-LHC at CERN or FAIR at GSI might have on relevant components.

These studies also allowed to identify a number of important thresholds and behaviours, as well as of influencing parameters, which should be further investigated in additional irradiation campaigns in the near future [41].

References

- [1] A. Bertarelli, “Beam-Induced Damage Mechanisms and their Calculation” in Proceedings of the Joint International Accelerator School: Beam Loss and Accelerator Protection, Newport Beach, United States, 5–14 November 2014, edited by R. Schmidt, CERN-2016-002 (CERN, Geneva, 2016), pp. 159 – 227, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5170/CERN-2016-002>
- [2] D. Kiselev. “Activation and radiation damage in the environment of hadron accelerators”. In: arXiv preprint arXiv:1303.6520 (2013).
- [3] A. Lechner *et al.*, Irradiation effect simulations, Deliverable 17.2, ARIES Technical report, 2021.
- [4] N.V. Mokhov and F Cerutti. “Beam-Material Interaction”. In: arXiv preprint arXiv:1608.02476 (2016).
- [5] T. Spina. “Proton irradiation effects on Nb3Sn wires and thin platelets in view of High Luminosity LHC upgrade”. PhD thesis, University of Geneva, Switzerland. PhD thesis. 2015.
- [6] J. Guardia-Valenzuela *et al.* “Development and properties of high thermal conductivity molybdenum carbide-graphite composites”. In: Carbon 135 (2018), pp. 72–84.
- [7] S. Redaelli *et al.*, Staged implementation of low-impedance collimation in IR7: plans for LS2. Tech. rep. 2019.
- [8] S. Redaelli *et al.*, “Cleaning insertions and collimation challenges”. In: The High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider: The New Machine for Illuminating the Mysteries of Universe. World Scientific, 2015, pp. 215–241.
- [9] S.A. Antipov *et al.* “Transverse beam stability with low-impedance collimators in the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider: Status and challenges”. In Physical Review Accelerators and Beams 23.3 (2020), p. 034403.
- [10] D.J. Mazey. “Fundamental aspects of high-energy ion-beam simulation techniques and their relevance to fusion materials studies”. In: Journal of nuclear materials 174.2-3 (1990), pp. 196–209.
- [11] SJ Jepeal, Lance Snead, and ZS Hartwig. “Intermediate energy proton irradiation: rapid, high-fidelity materials testing for fusion and fission energy systems”. In: Materials & Design (2020), p. 109445.
- [12] N Galy *et al.* “Ion irradiation used as surrogate of neutron irradiation in graphite: consequences on 14 C and 36 Cl behavior and structural evolution”. In: JNuM 502 (2018), pp. 20–29.
- [13] "FLUKA.CERN website," [Online]. Available: <https://fluka.cern>.
- [14] T. T. Böhlen, F. Cerutti, M. P. W. Chin, A. Fassò, A. Ferrari, P. G. Ortega, A. Mairani, P. R. Sala, G. Smirnov and V. Vlachoudis, "The FLUKA Code: Developments and Challenges for High Energy and Medical Applications," Nuclear Data Sheets, vol. 120, pp. 211-214, 2014.
- [15] G. Battistoni, T. Boehlen, F. Cerutti, P. W. Chin, L. S. Esposito, A. Fassò, A. Ferrari, A. Lechner, A. Empl, A. Mairani, A. Mereghetti, P. G. Ortega, J. Ranft, S. Roesler, P. R. Sala, V. Vlachoudis and G. Smirnov, "Overview of the FLUKA code," Annals of Nuclear Energy, vol. 82, pp. 10-18, 2015.
- [16] M. Tomut, C. Accettura, P. Simon, P. Bolz and M. Hoffer, "Irradiation campaigns at GSI for radiation hardness studies," ARIES Consortium, Milestone MS59, 2019.
- [17] C. Accettura, "Investigation of radiation damage effects on HL-LHC collimator materials," Politecnico di Milano, Milano (Italy), submitted 2021.
- [18] J. A. Thornton, “High rate sputtering techniques”. Thin Solid Films 1981, 80, 1–11.

- [19] Kouznetsov, *et al.*, Novel pulsed magnetron sputter technique utilizing very high target power densities. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 1999, 122, 290–293.
- [20] C. Accettura *et al.* “Resistivity Characterization of Molybdenum-Coated Graphite-Based Substrates for High-Luminosity LHC Collimators”. In: *Coatings* 10.4 (2020), p. 361.
- [21] M.A. Pimenta *et al.* “Studying disorder in graphite-based systems by Raman spectroscopy”. In: *Physical chemistry chemical physics* 9.11 (2007), pp. 1276–1290.
- [22] A.C. Ferrari. “Raman spectroscopy of graphene and graphite: Disorder, electron–phonon coupling, doping and nonadiabatic effects”. In: *Solid state communications* 143.1-2 (2007), pp. 47–57.
- [23] Andrea C Ferrari and John Robertson. “Interpretation of Raman spectra of disordered and amorphous carbon”. In: *Physical review B* 61.20 (2000), p. 14095.
- [24] DM Hembree *et al.* “Raman spectroscopy of C-irradiated graphite”. In: *MRS Online Proceedings Library Archive* 279 (1992).
- [25] Kazutaka Nakamura and Masahiro Kitajima. “Ion-irradiation effects on the phonon correlation length of graphite studied by Raman spectroscopy”. In: *Physical Review B* 45.1 (1992), p. 78.
- [26] Jie Liu *et al.* “STM and Raman spectroscopic study of graphite irradiated by heavy ions”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 212 (2003), pp. 303–307.
- [27] Jie Liu *et al.* “STM and Raman spectroscopic study of graphite irradiated by heavy ions”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 212 (2003), pp. 303–307.
- [28] PingHeng Tan *et al.* “Resonantly enhanced Raman scattering and high-order Raman spectra of single-walled carbon nanotubes”. In: *Applied physics letters* 75.11 (1999), pp. 1524–1526.
- [29] T Jawhari, A Roid, and J Casado. “Raman spectroscopic characterization of some commercially available carbon black materials”. In: *Carbon* 33.11 (1995), pp. 1561–1565.
- [30] Mirosława Pawlyta, Jean-Noël Rouzaud, and Stanislaw Duber. “Raman microspectroscopy characterization of carbon blacks: Spectral analysis and structural information”. In: *Carbon* 84 (2015), pp. 479–490.
- [31] Keisuke Niwase. “Raman spectroscopy for quantitative analysis of point defects and defect clusters in irradiated graphite”. In: *International Journal of Spectroscopy* 2012 (2012).
- [32] K Niwase, T Tanabe, and I Tanaka. “Annealing experiment of ion-irradiated graphite by laser Raman spectroscopy”. In: *Journal of nuclear materials* 191(1992), pp. 335–339.
- [33] Christopher M Barr *et al.* “Interplay between grain boundaries and radiation damage”. In: *JOM* 71.4 (2019), pp. 1233–1244.
- [34] A. Kurtulus *et al.* “Detailed Electromagnetic Characterisation of HL-LHC Low Impedance Collimators”. In: presented at the 12th Int. Particle Accelerator Conf. (IPAC’21) (Campinas, Brazil). JACoW Publishing, May 2021.
- [35] N. Solieri, "Update on BLIP irradiation tests and RaDIATE activities," in 2nd ARIES WP17 (PowerMat) Annual Meeting, Geneva, Switzerland, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/938208>, 2020.
- [36] M. Pasquali, A. Bertarelli *et al.*, "Dynamic Response of Advanced Materials Impacted by Particle Beams: The MultiMat Experiment". *Journal of Dynamic Behavior of Materials* (2019) 5:266–295. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40870-019-00210-1>
- [37] Kitzmantel M., (2015) Developments and Novelties in Thermal Management by RHP-Technology. EuCARD-2 Workshop on Applications of Thermal Management Materials, CERN, Switzerland.

- [38] M. Portelli *et al.*, "Thermomechanical Characterisation of Copper Diamond and Benchmarking with the MultiMat Experiment", *Shock and Vibration*, Vol. 2021, Article ID 8879400. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8879400>
- [39] A. Prosvetov, G. Hamaoui, N. Horny *et al.*, "Degradation of Thermal Transport Properties in Fine-grained Isotropic Graphite Exposed to Swift Heavy Ion Beams," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 184, pp. 187–198, 2020.
- [40] P Bolz, P Drechsel, A Prosvetov, P Simon, C Trautmann, M Tomut, Dynamic Radiation Effects Induced by Short-Pulsed GeV U-Ion Beams in Graphite and h-BN Targets, *Shock and Vibration* 2021.
- [41] Pascal Simon, Philipp Drechsel, Peter Katrik, Kay-Obbe Voss, Philipp Bolz, Fiona J. Harden, Michael Guinchard, Yacine Kadi, Christina Trautmann, Marilena Tomut, Dynamic Response of Graphitic Targets with Tantalum Cores Impacted by Pulsed 440-GeV Proton Beams, *Shock and Vibration* 2021.